

WAYS TO PREVENT THE ADDICTION OF YOUNG PEOPLE TO SOCIAL NETWORKS

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Abstract

Global development is widely created for humanity. The discovery of the Internet led to the creation of social networks and the acceleration of information acquisition. The acceleration of information forces affects the outlook of young people with its high quality. The article describes the quality of social network and site addiction of young people.

Key words: online communication, network culture, virtual slavery, internet addiction, computer-communication, memory, media education.

INTRODUCTION

The spiritual worldview of young people in society is associated with the quality of education and training. The globalization of information technologies, the computerization of the education system create an opportunity to seriously satisfy the need of young people in social networks. The system of higher education is equipped with high-quality electronic devices, with unlimited Internet connection, and brings the information virtual space of young people into the educational environment. The freedom to receive, share and impart information is reflected in the behavior of students.

LITERATURE REVIEW

"Third wave" in society's informatization, social problems of young people's use of information technologies, information security, addiction to computer games M. Dalimova, L. Nigmatullina, Qalandarova conducted dissertation studies within the framework of psychology and identification of the impact on the psyche of young students.¹ The scientific analysis of foreign and national literature is in areas such as informationalization of society, information security, computer games, Internet or computer communication, psychology of dependence on social networks is researched, but the dependence of young people on social networks is not put on the agenda by the authors as a research subject. In this sense, the popularization of electronic devices among young people, the serious growth of students' need for the Internet, and their communication to social networks through computers and other electronic devices define information addiction as a philosophical problem.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

As a result of the fact that the opportunity to communicate on the Internet through computers and mobile phones is provided to young people, leaving their fists to computers and mobile phones, there is a retreat of young people from ethical standards in communication on

information sites in the systems "Personal-virtual world" and "Personal and users ". The educational policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is aimed at creating conditions for information and communication technologies in highly qualified professional training of students. This situation is related to the problem of Internet addiction in connection with the formation of a communicative situation of student youth associated with social networks, and the study of a healthy lifestyle of young people is methodologically appropriate. The social danger of the problem of Internet addiction is manifested in the fact that the number of students and young people is growing day by day. In 1996, psychiatrist Ivan Goldberg introduced into scientific circulation the content of "Internet addiction" and the state of Internet communication as a psychological pathology. He meant that people would lose their professional and social activities as a result of using the Internet. And it was the fact that a person entered the news space with his fingers, thinking and not thinking. Psychologist T. Akhryamkina defined Internet addiction as a state of dependence of young people on social networks, the inability to give it up and a mental disorder that cannot be eliminated in time.² Students do not even realize that due to the uncontrollability of youth, they have become stable in the state of Internet communication, spend a lot of time in front of the monitor and especially become more in-depth in its use. As a result, Internet addiction among young people is an indicator of the manifestation of educational gaps in the family environment, in the field of education, as well as the practical result of indifference to young people. It can be seen that Internet addiction is a complex psychological process of young people sitting at a computer and turning off reading literature from it³. At the same time, there are also opinions of experts on the socio-economically effective use of Internet addiction.⁴

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The found that the social exclusion of youth is moving to a number of sites on the Internet to fill educational gaps:

- acquaintance, exchange of information, debates, dissemination of information, participation in training sessions, receiving and submitting scientific assignments and tasks via telegram channels;
- Passion for films, melodies and songs, computer games;
- can be grouped into Internet gambling games, advertising channels, partially pornographic images.

Students access popular Internet sites through social networks and rely on virtual communication, research shows that student youth exhibit features of social exclusion. Its main aspects are the decline of the student's scientific and creative activity, leaving the faculty, term papers and social work in the group, eventually shutting down, serious activity in conversations on a computer, mobile device, Internet sites, a tendency to communicate online with friends. y the aspect of the student's inability to learn lessons, manifested in aggressive behavior in conversations with teachers and teachers.

The communication of young people in social networks does not realize that, although they are part of a unique information resource system and continuously work in it, they are in a unique space. The Internet does not allow the perception of virtual space. Creating an industrial system to attract young people to the roof of social networks does not allow you to get away from it. The Internet system creates an attractive immunity for the student, creating a wide range of opportunities and amenities for doing science, fulfilling educational requirements. The computer is becoming an integral part of education in the role of the second memory of young people, as it stores most of the textbooks, manuals and other electronic data necessary for teaching the student. The ability to create information from this information also helps the learner easily create learning resources. This factor also causes the student's dependence on the computer and social networks.

A number of conclusions were drawn based on the above thoughts and considerations:

First of all, the information space becomes the meaning of human life on a global scale, and the possibilities of its use are expanding due to the fact that it becomes a need of everyday life, even a vital necessity. The unique personal and collective morality of the information space requires a social virtual culture of Internet users. Internet addiction attracts a person with a wide range of diverse information, creates the opportunity to receive social information and messages, i.e. creates incomparable conditions for the spiritual and educational sphere of influence.

Secondly, the essence of the modern Internet is sites and portals, social networks. A person becomes a cyber-citizen of the world and moves to cosmological thinking. Ambivalence in the social mentality of a person seriously harms his spirit and health, forms a dependence on online communication. Online friends generate interest in a person by their "distance", "sweet talk" and gender. As a result, online social virtual connections such as "friend", "love", "religious" separate a person from reality and create another virtual "I".

Thirdly, the comprehensive financial and ideological support of social networks of transnational companies in the Internet world has an invisible impact on the risk of information dependence in exchange for threats and attacks. Addiction to social networks is a new social ideological level that arises from the Internet addiction of a person. And social dependence is the ideology of "social alienation", serving a certain programmed social ideological goal. This is due to the renewal of the psychological state, the "wear and tear" of an existing factor, or the pleasantness of connecting with a friend in an "attractive" space from a "social problem situation and a friend" at the same time.

Fourthly, the optional organization of media education courses and trainings on information security in the education system will give positive results in order to prevent young people from becoming dependent on social networks. Experience has confirmed the need for a radical renewal of spiritual and educational work in the education system. It is impossible to change the quality of education without changing the lives of young people with new interesting and meaningful forms of work with youth. First of all, spiritual leaders need to wait for instructions

"from above", to connect non-traditional innovative youth to the spiritual real world, from traditionalism dedicated to "holidays or solemn" days.

Fifthly, the example of the Facebook social network clearly demonstrates the high need of users for literacy in the national language, the need for enlightenment of philosophical thinking in thoughts and judgments. The author believes that it is necessary to continue the activities of spiritual figures and propagandists in social networks. It should be remembered that working in social networks requires a creative approach, ethical tact and behavior, tolerance. It is a continuous learning process, just like a slave who has been addicted for many years cannot be freed overnight.

Sixth, since the informatization of society is a process of global development of science and technology, the promotion of its positive and negative sides and features is a social task. The organization of youth centers for information and communication technologies, their educational activities and competitions and events on spiritual and educational information technologies, the information security system, especially personal protective equipment against social threats, prevents the formation of destructive behavior in adolescents. In the conditions of the information society, the dependence of young people on religious extremist networks in social networks is extremely dangerous, and its threat has acquired socio-political significance. Although the work of computer and Internet systems in the education system makes it easier for students to master the technical sciences, the role of the spiritual and educational conversation of the teacher face to face in the social sciences has a special educational effect and positively affects the level of education and worldview. In education, the student is formed in an environment not only of professionalization, but also of socialization.

Internet addiction requires a computer device and mobile phones, so students are in the category with full access to electronic information devices. In the education system, the student has the opportunity to search and find educational information, work and master it independently according to the program. The researcher emphasizes that the convenience of Internet communication has become an integral part of the lifestyle of young people in the context of the global nature of social information. Labor activity, education and upbringing, living conditions of youth cannot be imagined without Internet communication. The teacher M. Kuronov spoke about the positive and negative impact of networks covering all spheres of human life on the education of children in the following features "... endless informal communication in real time;

Entertainment games, movies, music, video games;

Advertising and commercial use;

Development of intellectual and creative abilities

Enables distance learning.⁵

In the process of informing society, online computer communication creates an opportunity for students to carry out individual personal or group collective communication in the virtual space. Therefore, in connection with the dynamic growth of the desire to enter the computer

social network, young people create new socio-organizational ties in their social relations. The ease of use of a computer and its revolutionary versatility compared to a portable typewriter will delight young people. As a result, they have to sit for a long time because they cannot control the time spent at the computer. Texts, clips and other graphics on the monitor screen negatively affect the human brain, and the light emitted by the screen harms the eyes. Prolonged sitting of the spine in young people causes various diseases, and inactivity also destroys cardiovascular activity. Medical representatives confirmed that the constant work of young people at the computer causes mental pathology. While the Finnish government disqualifies young people diagnosed with computer addiction as unfit for military service, medical clinics that treat Internet addiction operate in the US and China.

The most important feature of the Renaissance reforms was the elimination of the serious backwardness of the human factor, especially spiritual growth, in comparison with the incomparable growth of science and technology. On the other hand, globalization and mass information technologies cover all spheres of public life, making the need for spirituality and enlightenment as an urgent problem more than ever. Although the problems of spirituality and enlightenment are studied in the social and human sciences, they cause heated debate, but there is no consensus on their essence. These values are the pedagogical category of priority in the formation of civil society, the national idea.

Conclusion/Rekommendations.

The formation of religious sites, channels and blogs in social networks indicates a lack of religious enlightenment in educational enlightenment, the passage of religiosity in a complex process, lagging behind information culture and enlightenment of youth in social development. The activation of religious channels in social networks attracts young people with the virtualization of the real religious reality in the life of society, the freedom and lack of control of discussions in it. The structure of the Internet network and channels is based on the "Sovereign and subordinate" standard in terms of social influence, and its manager is under the control of the leaders, such as "Herald, moderator, administrator", and the members are also determined by the membership status and responsibilities, such as " guest, group, veteran, VIP". The popularization of religious traditions and values, the strengthening of stereotypes of religiosity in socialization, the formation of real scientific enlightenment against the backdrop of propaganda of universal religiosity, acceptable youth that does not require proof, is an important educational factor. In order to prevent religious fanaticism in social networks, there is a growing need to post religious and educational exercises on the Internet and launch sites and blogs in national networks that are compatible with the interests of the national idea. The analysis of social problems from the point of view of the worldview complex national-religious culture is an important educational aspect in eliminating the virtual dependence of young people on Internet networks. The cultural outlook of young people is expanding in conversations about the meaning of human life, the purpose of life, against the background of distracting young people with banal, meaningless and easily digestible topics.⁶

Based on the study of media education in the prevention of university students' dependence on social networks, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The globalization of information technology opens up a new era in the quality of human life in terms of the distribution, reception, storage and transmission of information using high-quality electronic devices in all areas of public life. The Internet creates a single information space on a global scale and fully covers the sphere of production and education. At the same time, the speed of dissemination of information is growing immeasurably, and the information base of the Internet determines the socio-cultural level of the post-industrial society by the amount of knowledge. A number of countries around the world have become leaders in the online education market and have become business leaders thanks to transnational educational services. Information, news and other sources of the Internet can be positive or negative, and at the same time they can represent the interests of certain countries, societies and groups.

2. According to its content, the Internet is a collection of various information social networks, among which the "attractiveness" of Odnoklassniki, Twitter, Instagram, Fibuka, Tik-Tok is based on the will and interests of students and youth attracts its expediency. The interest of young people in the user of the online form of communication is due to freedom in the virtual system "I and network users" in social networks, the lack of control over the aspect of mutual "friend", "religious", "reverence" of others. Users. The presence of all information about artistic and creative works, films, songs, hobbies in social networks attracts a person, and the student becomes attached to it. Computer dependence of students, equipping with a modern information system in the field of education, Internet communication in its essence, organization of the media educational process based on information technologies form an electronic base.

3. In the modern information society, computers and the Internet penetrate into all spheres of human life, and student youth take the lead in using the Internet among social groups of society. The dependence of young people on social networks should be understood as the uncontrolled use of a computer by students, communication of the virtual world by connecting to the Internet on the basis of a computer device, i.e. that is, the process of obtaining, storing and transmitting information. In this sense, a computer or other device connected to the Internet introduces young people into a virtual world.

4. The transition from the real world to the virtual world with the requirements of social norms and criteria in the use of social networks by young people, their constant presence in front of the computer is recognized as a mental and spiritual pathology in foreign countries. . Because the user's vision and inactivity cause diseases such as the spine, back, and circulatory disorders in the internal organs. As a result, it causes stress and mental depression of the human brain. In the educational process of young people, along with a number of complications, there is a fall from collectivity to individuality, that is, social alienation. Internet addiction forms the mental dependence of young people at the level of social fanaticism, and their behavior manifests itself in such deviant tendencies as selfishness and selfishness.

5. Internet addiction creates a serious need for information in the communication of social networks of young people, not only education, but also a situation of meaningless familiarization with information about various social phenomena and events. Its content is a disconnection from real life in the conditions of freedom of cyberspace, in a new idealless

virtual space in social networks. Therefore, the prevention of Internet addiction is carried out by paying attention to young people and preventing the social exclusion of young people through cultural and educational activities in various regions.

6. Social networks are connected to a morally alien environment on the basis that they have a certain status and goals in relation to leaders, such as moderators, messengers, administrators. As a result, student youth falls into the trap of extremist and terrorist movements on a virtual religious-national basis, and the religious community of a virtual social network

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